
PROFITABILITY AND TECHNICAL EFFICIENCY OF DRY SEASON VEGETABLE PRODUCTION UNDER TROPICAL CONDITIONS.

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ABSTRACT

Vegetables are complementary foods of the first order and are more important to man's health than product of animal origin since nobody will suffer from eating quite large different vegetables whereas eating too much meat is pointless and may cause health problems. The study was designed to examine the profitability and measure the level of technical efficiency of dry season vegetable producers using stochastic frontier production function. A purposive sampling technique was used to select 60 vegetable farmers in the study area. Cost and return analysis revealed that dry season vegetable enterprise is profitable in the area, with positive gross margin/ha ₦47,372.08 (\$364.40), positive Net profit/ha ₦43,957.08 (\$338.13) and a benefit-cost ratio of 2.18. The estimated farm technical efficiency ranges from 75% to 98% with a mean of 92%. This indicates that ample opportunity exists for the producers to increase their productivity and income through a more efficiency utilization of productive resources. Inefficiency determinants are all directly related to technical efficiency but are not significantly determined the technical efficiency of the producers.

KEY WORDS: profitability, technical efficiency, dry-season, farms.

INTRODUCTION

Vegetable are generally regarded as essential herbaceous plant having high moisture content in their fresh forms with considerable quantities of vitamin, A,B,C,D,E and K, which help to protect the body against diseases and contribute in no small measures to good health (Agusiobo 1984). Vegetables are therefore, complementary foods of the first order and are much more important to man's health than product of animal origin since nobody will suffer from eating quite large amount of different vegetables whereas eating too much meat is pointless and may cause health problems.

The daily need for vegetables as recommended by FAO and reported by Wainjemberg (1981), is normally 150-250grammes per person. This is expected to provide balanced diet needed by people particularly in diet characterized by low inclusion of meat and other animal proteins (Afolabi and Ayinde, 1996). According to the CBN statistical Bulletin (1998), the production level of vegetable crops in Nigeria is 3.82 metric tones in 1997. although they are vast inter-country differences, current vegetable supplies in many developing countries including Nigeria cannot even meet one half of FAO recommendation. Olayide (1980) projected vegetable food deficits to reach 1.778 metric tones by 1995, the situation is not so different even till today

Apart from the generally problems facing food crops producers in Nigeria, vegetables and fruit crops farmers still faces other unique problems due to high perish ability of this products which warranted that the product must be transported quickly to the point of consumption in other to reduce losses due to spoilage. In some cases up to 40% post harvest loses had been recorded for some vegetables and fruits.

Dry season vegetables production makes it possible for producers to grow the crop all year round along non-saline river bank, valley and non-waterlogged swamps. The most important requirement for dry season production is availability of water source for irrigation purpose.

The recent Fadama II project jointly sponsored by World Bank and Africa Development Banks is a step in the right direction towards encouraging dry season farming especially vegetables production.

Problem of low productivity and non-availability of vegetable all year round being experienced by the producers and consumers of dry season vegetable is due partly to inefficient management of resources/inputs available to the producers especially the chemical input. This study therefore aim at examine profitability and technical efficiency of dry season vegetables production in Nigeria.

The specific objectives of the study are to;

- (1) Identify the socio-economic characteristics of dry season vegetables producers.
- (2) Examine the cost and returns to dry season vegetable farms.
- (3) Estimate the technical efficiency indices of each decision-making unit. (i.e each firm in vegetable production).

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The efficiency of a firm is the ability to derive from a fixed amount of inputs the greatest amount of output possible. An efficient firm is that which, given a state of technical know-how, can produce a given quantity of goods by using the least quantity of input possible.

The efficiency of a firm has two components, this are technical and allocative efficiency. Technical efficiency is the ability to produce a given level of output with a minimum quantity of input under a given technology, while allocative efficiency measures the degree of success in achieving the best combination of different inputs in producing a specific level of output, having regard to the relative prices of these inputs.

The first analysis of efficiency measures started with Farrell (1957), who drawing inspiration from Debreu (1951) and Koopmans (1961) proposed a division of efficiency into two components as started before.

The stochastic frontier model was independently proposed by Aigner, Lovell and Schmidt (1977) and Meeusen and Van den Broeck (1977). According to (Onyenweaku and Nwaru 2005), as stochastic frontier production function is defined by;

$$Y = f(X_i, B_i) \exp(V_i - U_i), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n$$

Where; Y_i is output of the i th farm

X_i is the vector of input quantities used by the i th farm.

B_i , is a vector of unknown parameters to be estimated

V_i is a symmetric error, which accounts for random variations in output due to factors beyond the control of the producers.

While U_i is a non negative random variable representing inefficiency in production relative to the stochastic frontier. The random error V_i is assumed to be independently and identically distributed as $N(0, \sigma^2)$ random variables independent of the U_i which are assumed to be non negative truncation of the $N(0, \sigma^2)$ distribution or have exponential distribution.

Technical efficiency is define as,

$$TE = Y_i/Y_i^* = f(X_i, B) \exp(V_i - U_i) / f(X_i, B) \exp(V_i) = \exp(-U_i)$$

Where Y_i is the observed output

Y_i^* is the frontier output

The parameters of the stochastic frontier production function are estimated using the maximum likelihood method.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

The study was carried out in Osogbo Local Government Area of Osun State, Nigeria with the headquarter at Oke-bale, in Osogbo. Osogbo has a population of 180,000 people according to 1991 census. Osogbo is situated on a raised land, which is well over 500m above the sea level.

Osogbo Local Government has a farm settlement which is Agric. Oke-Osun farm settlement and is at the extreme of the local government. It has more than 15 rural communities.

Agriculturally, a bench survey of the territory conducted by the Osogbo ADP in 1992 revealed that maize (*Zea Mays Linneans*), cassava (*Manihot esculenta crantz*) Yam (*Dioscovea Votundata Poit*), melon (*cucumis melo Linneans*), Sorghum (*Sorghum bicolar moanch*) and Rice (*Oryza Sativa Linneans*) are among major crops grown by over sixty percent of the producers. Other crops grown include vegetable, sugar, cane, millet, cowpea, soybean and groundnut etc.

Population of the Study, Sampling Procedure and Sampling Size.

Population of the study are all dry season vegetable producers in Osogbo Local Government Area.

The purposive sampling procedure was adopted for the study. Based on the information earlier collected from the Osun State Agricultural Development Programme (OSADEP) officials, farm settlement and Oke-pupa rural community farmers who engage themselves in dry season vegetable were purposively selected based on the fact that these two communities have irrigation schemes and formed the majority of registered vegetable growers for this study.

Method of Data Collection and Analysis

Interview schedule was used to collected data from the selected respondents. Data collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequency table and percentages. Stochastic frontier production function was used to examine the technical efficiency of the respondents, while budgetary analysis was used to determine the profitability (or otherwise) of the enterprise.

Model Specification

The stochastic frontier production function of the Cobb Douglas types was specified for this study. Due to its advantages over other functional forms, which includes the fact that it regression coefficients is the same as it elasticities and it return to scale value is equal to the sum of it elasticity's values. It is widely used in the frontier production function studies (Kalirajan and Finn, 1983). The model was specified as;

$$Y_i = B_0 + B_1 \log X_1 + B_2 \log X_2 + B_3 \log X_3 + B_4 + V_i + U_i \dots \dots \dots (i)$$

Where

Y = Yield (tones)

X₁ = Rent (₦)

X₂ = Seed (kg)

X₃ = Labour (manday)

X₅ = Chemical (litre)

I = 1,2,3 and 4

B₀, B₁ --- B₄ = Regression parameters.

V_i is the error component representing statistical wise and is assumed to follow, a normal distribution with mean zero and constant variance.

U_i is the error component representing the farm specific effect of technical efficiency.

The inefficiency model is stated as;

$$\mu = \delta_0 + \delta_1 Z_1 + \delta_2 Z_2 + \dots + \delta_4 Z_4 \dots \dots \dots (ii)$$

Where μ = Technical inefficiencies effect on the farm

Z_1 = Years of schooling

Z_2 = Other Occupation

Z_3 = Number of visitation by extension workers

Z_4 = Years of experience in vegetable production.

Z_5 = Years size (hectare)

Z_6 = Age (years)

Z_7 = Extent benefit (Yes = 1, No = 0)

Z_8 = Association benefit (Yes = 1, No = 0)

The Gross margin (Gm) is given as;

$$GM = TR - TFC \dots\dots\dots(iii)$$

And the Net profit is (NP) is given as;

$$NP = Gm - TFC$$

Where, TR is Total Revenue (₦). TVC is the total Variable Cost (₦), while TFC is the Total Fixed Cost (₦)

RESULTS AD DISCUSSION

(a) Socio- Economic Characteristics of Dry Season Vegetable Producers.

The socio- economic characteristics of respondents showed that majority (75%) were male, with modal age group between (51-60 years) accounting for forty percent of respondents as shown in Table 1. Table 1 also shows that majority (83.3%) of the farmers were married, while about sixty-seven percent of respondents pass through one form of education or the others. Most (40%) respondents have between 10-20 years experience in dry season vegetable production. Also from Table 1 about thirty two percent of the producers engage themselves in other occupation apart from farming. From the above analysis, it can be deduced that an average farmer is a male, in his middle age, stable, experience, full time farmers. He is also educated to a certain extent. These inefficiency variables suppose to have a positive impact in the producers' productivity and efficiency.

Table 2 shows that majority (91.7%) of dry season vegetable farmers belong to one association or the other and derived various benefit from such association. The major benefits derived by respondents are access to financial assistance, chemical input, technical information, marketing assistance and seed supply. Infact, about fifty-four percent of the respondents enjoy all the above benefits from their association. Table 2 also shows that most (63.3%) producers have contact with extension agents, and derived extension benefit like training and advices from their contact. The results from Table 2 also revealed that majority (84.9%) of the producers are small scale producers having less than five hectare in farm land.

TABLE 1: SOCIO ECONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE PRODUCERS

	Frequency	Percentage
SEX		
Male	45	75.0
Female	15	25.0
Total	60	1000
AGE (YEAR)		
Less than 3 year s	2	3.3
31 – 40	4	6.7
41 – 60	11	18.3
51 – 60	24	40.0
Above 60	19	31.7
Total	60	100
MARITAL STATUS		
Married	50	83.3
Divorced	3	5.0
Widow	7	1.7
Total	60	100
EDUCATION (YEARS)		
0	20	33.3
1 – 6	10	16.7
7 –12	17	28.3
13 – 15	10	16.7
16 – 18	3	5.0
Total	60	100
YEARS OF EXPERIENCE		
0	3	5.0
Less than 10	12	20.0
10 – 20	24	40.0
21 – 30	13	21.7
31 - 40	7	11.7
Total	60	100
OTHER OCCUPATION		
Yes	19	31.7
No	41	68.3
Total	60	100.00

Source: Field Survey 2010.

TABLE 2:-ACTIVITIES OF DRY SEASON VEGITABLE FARMERS PRODUCTION AND FARM SIZE.

	Frequency	Percentage
ASSOCIATION		
Yes	55	91.7
No	5	8.3
Total	60	100
ASSOCIATION BENEFIT		
Non	12	20.0
Chemical input	3	5.0
Financial assistance	7	11.7
Technical information	3	5.0
Seed supply	1	1.7
Marketing assistance	2	3.3
All of the above	32	53.2
Total	60	100
CONTACT WITH EXTENSION		
Yes	41	68.3
No	19	31.7
Total	60	100
EXTENSION BENEFIT		
Non	25	41.7
Training	0.7	11.7
Advices	7.28	46.6
Total	60	100
VEGETABLE FARM SIZE (HECTARE)		
1-5	51	84.9
6-10	09	15.1
Total	60	100

Source: Field survey, 2010.

Cost and Returns Analysis

The costs of vegetable production include the cost of fixed inputs (land and implements) and variable inputs such as seed, labour, and chemicals. All costs been computed per hectare. Table 3 shows that the total fixed cost was N 3,415.42, (\$26.27) while the total variable cost was N33,880.42,(\$286.88). The total revenue was N81,252.40 (\$625.01). Using the formula stated before in equation (iii). A positive gross margin N47,372.08 (\$364.40) and a positive Net profit N43,957.08 (\$338.13) was obtained. This shows that dry season vegetable production is profitable in the area. A benefit cost ration of 2.18 further confirm the above finding and revealed that for every naira (₦)/dollar (\$) invested in the enterprise ₦2.18 is realized as return.

TABLE 3: ANALYSIS OF COST AND RETURN FROM DRY SEASON VEGETABLE PRODUCTION PER HECTARE

	₦	₦
		81,252.50
Total revenue		
Cost		
(1) Variable Cost		
(a) Fertilizer/chemical	10,166.53	
(b) Hired labour	22,358.69	
(c) Seeds	1,355.20	
Total variable cost		<u>33,880.42</u>
Gross margin		47,372.08
(2) Fixed Costs		
depreciation		
(a) Land (Rent)	1,500	
(b) Hoes	320	
(c) Cutlass	595	
(d) Basket and Others	1,000	
Total fixed cost		3,415.00
Net profit		<u>37,295.42</u>
		<u>43,957.08</u>
Benefit cost ratio = $\frac{\text{Total Revenue}}{\text{Total Cost}}$		
B/C ratio = $\frac{\text{₦}51,252.50}{\text{₦}37,298.42}$	= 2.18 >1	

OLS AND MILE ANALYSIS

The ordinary least square (OLS) and the maximum likelihood estimate (MLE) of the production function parameters for dry seasonal vegetable production in Osogbo is presented in Table 4. A comparison of the function shows that stochastic production function has a higher intercept term than the OLS production function. All the variables included in the models followed the production expectation with the exception of labour and chemical inputs that has an inverse relationship with the yield.

In OLS models, labour is statistically significant at 1% level of probability, rent and seed also have significant impact on the yield. The coefficient of rent paid on land is 0.95, this implies that 1% increase in access to land will lead to about 0.9% increase in yield while reducing the chemical and labour input by 1% would lead to about 0.70% and 0.80% increase in yield. The sum of the regression coefficient (elasticities) in Cobb- Douglass gives the return to scale. The value of return to scale is - 0.13. This implies in decrease return to scale. That is a proportionate increases in all factors of production (fertilizer, labour, seed) resulted in less than proportionate (smaller) increase in vegetable output.

In MLE of the frontier production function estimate shows that sigma-square which indicates the goodness of fit and correction of distribution assumption is significantly different from zero. The variance ratios which measure the effect of technical efficiency in the variation of observed output has a value of 0.26. This shows that about 26% of the difference between the observed and production frontier output were due to differences in the farmers output of technical efficiency and not related to random variability. In MLE model, only seed have a coefficient that is significant at 1% level of probability. This implies that, if we increase seed input by 1%, it will lead to 0.42% increase in yield.

TABLE 4: ESTIMATION OF PRODUCTION FOR DRY SEASON VEGETABLE FARMERS

Variable	Parameter	Average OLS Function	Frontier Function (MLS)
Constant	b ₀	0.33 (3.60)*	0.42 (0.45)
Rent	b ₁	0.95 (3.12)*	0.92 (0.95)
Seed	b ₂	0.42 (3.53)*	0.42 (4.17)*
Labour	b ₃	-0.70 (-3.47)*	-0.70 (-0.70)
Chemical	b ₄	-0.80 (-0.32)	-0.80 (-0.80)
R ²		0.811	
F-ratio		30.180*	0.26
Signal (δ)			(0.030)
Gamma (γ)			0.50
Source: Field survey 2006			(0.500)

Figures in parentheses are t-ratio

* = significant at 1%

Estimates of Parameters of Technical Efficiency

The frequency distribution of technical efficiency of dry season vegetable producers in the study area is presented in Table 5, the individual technical efficiency indices range between 0.75 and 0.98. This shows that the efficiency of producers can still be improve on. Though most efficient farm is very close to the frontier, none of the producers was on the efficiency frontier. Inter-farm variation in technical efficient are very small as suggested by the small gap between the least efficiency index (0.70-0.79) and the highest efficiency index (0.90-0.99).

TABLE 5: FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION OF FARM SPECIFIES TECHNICAL EFFICIENCY

Efficiency	Frequency	Percentage
0.70-0.79	04	6.67
0.80-0.89	15	25.0
0.90-0.99	41	68.33
Total	60	100
Mean efficiencies = 0.92		

Source: Field survey, 2010

Source of Technical Efficiency

The effect of the selected socio-economic factors on the estimated technical efficiency was examined. It has observed that al the inefficiency determinations fitted in the model have positive but insignificant relationship with the technical efficiency, this implies that, though they tend to have a positive association with the technical indexes, they cannot significantly determined an improvement on productivity. Table 6 gives a better description of the inefficiency determinants.

TABLE 6: SOURCE OF TECHNICAL INEFFICIENCY

Variable	Parameter	Coefficient
Constant	Z ₀	0.16 (0.001)
Education	Z ₁	0.10 (0.103)
Other occupation	Z ₂	0.85 (0.009)
No of visitation by extensions workers	Z ₃	0.12 (0.012)
Years of Experience	Z ₄	0.82 (0.009)
Farm size	Z ₅	0.73 (0.073)
Age	Z ₆	1.94 (0.098)
Extension Benefit	Z ₇	0.21 (0.002)
Membership of Association	Z ₈	0.86 (0.089)

Source: Field survey 2010

Figures in parentheses are t-ratio

CONCLUSION

The result of this study show that technical efficiency in dry season vegetable production in Oshogbo Local Government area, Nigeria ranges between 75% and 98% with a mean of 92%. This suggested that there are substantial opportunities to increase productivity and income of the dry season vegetable producers in the study area through a more efficient utilization of productive resources.

All the inefficiency determinants are all directly related to technical efficiency but are not significantly determined the technical efficiency of the producers.

The result of the study also revealed that dry season vegetable production in the area is profitable since the gross margin/ha (N47, 372.08) and the Net profit/ha (N 43,957.08) are positive. The benefit cost ratio of 2.18 indicates that for every naira invested in the business N2.18 is realized as returns from investment.

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